

Women Empowerment through Self Help Groups: An Analytical Study

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Abstract

Women's entrepreneurship is seen as a way to help the economy grow because it creates jobs for women and others, as well as different ways for society to manage, organize, and run businesses. It also helps the family and the community as a whole, and helps to reduce poverty. The rise of SHG's is a sign that women are stepping out of their comfort zones and keeping their place in society.

This paper is all about how Self Help Groups (SHGs) can help empower women. It's a great way for the poor to get involved in development. SHGs are a great way for poor women to learn how to save money and become financially independent. Women SHGs are a different kind of intervention than most other programs. They're a great way to help reduce poverty, promote women's development, and empower them. Women SHGs have made it easier for women to be involved in the political, economic, social, and cultural life of rural India.

Women in India now participate fully in areas such as education, sports, politics, media, art and culture, service sectors, science and technology, etc. One of the most famous female business success stories is the Shri Mahila Griha Udyog Lijjat Papad. Another example we can take of the successful Mushroom farmer and entrepreneur of Nalanda District under leadership of Anita Devi.

Keywords Self Help Groups, SHGs, Women Entrepreneurship, Women Empowerment, Women's Developments, Financially Independent.

Introduction

It's no secret that poverty, education, unemployment, and lack of education are the main factors that have caused women to be dispossessed in many developing countries. In India, women are often left to fend for themselves and have limited opportunities to participate in social and economic life. Poor skills, low wages, hunger, illiteracy, and domestic violence are just a few of the obstacles they face. So, when poverty became a bigger problem in our country, economic planners came up with different ways to help people get out of it. The Government of India started various programs to help people out of poverty and get gainful employment, which paved the way for the Self Help Groups movement to help poor women groups get out of poverty.

Aim of study

This study seeks to evaluate the effects of SHG on women-promoted SHGs. The objectives of the study include assessing the impact of bank linkages on SHG members, assessing the socio-economic characteristics of SHG members, assessing the capacity building and training needs of SHGs for women, and assessing the leadership qualities of SHG members to engage in higher income generating activities.

Review of Literature

This study focused on the role of SHG's in women's empowerment, specifically in terms of economic and social empowerment, as well as poverty eradication. It's important to look back at the literature that has been written on this topic, like S. Harpal Singh's SHG: A Tool of Women's Empowerment. It's been argued that participation, which can be done in many different ways, is the best way to empower women. Whether it's voting and

having an opinion, or running for office with a chance of getting elected, political participation is a huge part of empowering people. Women in thrift groups are becoming increasingly influential in the political arena since the movement started in the 1990s. Even illiterate tribal women have become community leaders of national importance.

According to Malik (2006), SHG micro enterprises meet four objectives: Poverty reduction; Employment generation; Enterprise development; Empowerment of women; Diversifying household economic activities; Importance of productive activities; Economic security; Micro enterprises had a significant impact on women's empowerment. According to NARAYANA RINGDY et al., 2005, Women empowerment can only be achieved when society acknowledges women as one of the social partners; Ensures equal rights for women; Facilitates equal education and health; Offers equal and effective participation. According to Suganya M (2006). In his study, SriRam M.S. (2005) looked at how microfinance and the state have worked together in India since the early 90s. He found that the state has been doing a lot to make it easier for people in poverty to access financial services, which helps the state make the most of the resources it has available for the poor. He also found that Self Help Groups have a big impact on poverty alleviation, as they not only help reduce poverty, but also teach people how to start their own businesses and help them work together.

Main Text

Concept of Women Empowerment

Women empowerment is the process of increasing the participation of women and girls in society, and improving their social, economic, and political status. It is a complex and multifaceted issue, with a variety of factors that contribute to it.

One of the most important factors in women empowerment is access to education and employment. When women are educated and have the opportunity to work, they are able to earn their own income and have a greater say in their own lives. They are also more likely to be involved in decision-making at the household and community levels.

Another important factor in women empowerment is access to credit and financial services. When women have access to credit, they are able to start their own businesses or invest in their education or training. This can lead to increased income and improved livelihoods.

The relationship between women's empowerment and social development has been a major theme in studies of any nation's overall development. Women comprise of half of the country's population, yet, they have limited control over income. Most women remain confined to a narrow range of female low-income activities resulting in gender discrimination. Poverty and unemployment are the major problems of any under-developed countries, to which India is no exception.

There is no doubt that women are key to the development of any society. Studies have shown that women's economic and social power has a huge impact on the economy. Women's empowerment through SHGs could lead to benefits not just for the individual members, but for the whole family and community. This study wanted to see how the members of the women's SHG were doing and what the social effects of being part of the group were.

Self-Help Groups (SHGs)

Self-help groups (SHGs) are one of the most effective ways to empower women. SHGs are groups of women who come together to save money, borrow money from each other, and start small businesses. SHGs provide women with a safe space to learn about financial management, business skills, and leadership. They also provide women with a support network of other women who can offer encouragement and advice.

There are many examples of how SHGs have empowered women in India. In one study, it was found that women who were members of SHGs were more likely to be employed, have higher incomes, and have better access to healthcare and education than women who were not members of SHGs. Another study found that SHGs had a positive impact on women's decision-making power within the household.

SHGs are a powerful tool for women empowerment. They provide women with the resources and support they need to improve their lives. SHGs are also a cost-effective way to promote women's empowerment.

SHG is a small group of rural poor, who have voluntarily come forward to form a group for improvement of the social and economic status of the members. It can be formal (registered) or informal. Members of SHG agree to save regularly and contribute to a common fund. The members agree to use this common fund and such other funds (like grants and loans from banks), which they may receive as a group, to give small loans to needy members as per the decision of the group.

Need of SHGs

Poor women in rural areas are often left behind due to a variety of factors, like being socially backward, not educated, having low motivation, and not having a strong economic foundation. But when they work together, they have the power to overcome these obstacles. This is why SHGs are so important, as they can: help the individual members of the group to use their skills to improve their own economic situation, save money, and use local resources for group purposes. They can also help raise awareness of rights that can help with financial assistance. They can also identify problems, analyze them, and find solutions. Finally, they can act as media for the village's economic development, build trust and confidence, and develop leadership qualities.

SHGs can offer a number of benefits for women. They can provide a safe space to share experiences and feelings, and to connect with other women who understand what they are going through. SHGs can also provide practical support, such as childcare or transportation. And they can offer a sense of community and belonging, which can be especially important for women who feel isolated or alone.

Here are some of the benefits of SHGs for women:

- i. Support: SHGs can provide a safe space for women to share their experiences and feelings, and to connect with other women who understand what they are going through.
 - ii. Practical support: SHGs can also provide practical support, such as childcare or transportation.
 - iii. Sense of community: SHGs can offer a sense of community and belonging, which can be especially important for women who feel isolated or alone.
 - iv. Empowerment: SHGs can empower women by providing them with the opportunity to learn new skills, develop their confidence, and take control of their lives.
 - v. Advocacy: SHGs can advocate for the needs of women in their community and work to improve the lives of women.
- For women joining an SHG can be a great way to connect with other women, get support, and learn new skills.

Findings

The majority of the population is between the ages of 20 and 40, and while a lot of them have at least some basic education, a lot of them don't even have a high school education. After joining SHGs, women saw a big jump in their employment and income, and their standard of living improved. They also felt more empowered, had more self-esteem, and were more aware of what was going on in the world. There was also a strong connection between the group members and taking money from the groups, and they not only empowered themselves, but also the community by being role models. SHGs can be a powerful tool for women's empowerment, but they also face some challenges.

One of the biggest challenges for SHGs is access to capital. Women in developing countries often have difficulty accessing formal financial services, such as loans from banks. SHGs can help women to overcome this challenge by providing them with a way to save money and borrow money from each other.

Another challenge for SHGs is the lack of education and training for women. Many women in developing countries do not have access to education or training, which can make it difficult for them to participate in SHGs. SHGs can help to address this challenge by providing women with education and training on financial management, business skills, and leadership.

Despite the challenges, SHGs can be a powerful tool for women's empowerment. SHGs can help women to improve their financial situation, build businesses, and gain leadership skills. SHGs can also help to reduce poverty and improve the lives of women and their families.

Here are some of the opportunities that SHGs can provide for women:

1. Financial empowerment: SHGs can help women to save money, borrow money, and invest in their businesses. This can lead to improved financial security and independence.
2. Economic empowerment: SHGs can help women to start and grow businesses. This can lead to increased income and employment opportunities.
3. Social empowerment: SHGs can provide a space for women to connect with each other, learn new skills, and build confidence. This can lead to increased social participation and leadership.
4. Political empowerment: SHGs can help women to raise their voices and advocate for their rights. This can lead to increased political participation and representation.

Overall, SHGs can be a powerful tool for women's empowerment. They can help women to improve their financial situation, build businesses, gain leadership skills, and reduce poverty.

Conclusion

Self-help groups (SHGs) should take the initiative to provide minimal education to their members, as the majority of them are illiterate. To increase employment and income among rural women, government and non-governmental organizations should create programs to encourage entrepreneurship among them. The analysis suggests that SHG members have contributed to rural development, and thus the level of awareness of their work should be increased. Furthermore, SHG members should promote the products they produce by conducting exhibitions in both rural and urban areas, in order to increase awareness and provide rural women members with a wider range of exposure. This, in turn, will lead to more jobs, income and economic growth in rural areas, thereby reducing the regional income and wealth imbalances across the country.

Women in India now participate fully in areas such as education, sports, politics, media, art and culture, service sectors, science and technology, etc. One of the most famous female business success stories is the Shri Mahila Griha Udyog Lijjat Papad. In 1990s, grants from foreign donor agencies enabled the formation of new women-oriented NGOs. Self-help groups and NGOs such as Self Employed Women's Association (SEWA) have played a major role in the advancement of women's rights in India.

The economic development of India is contingent upon the productivity of both men and women's labor. In the early days of India, women were confined to the home and were largely ruled by men. However, in recent times, the social and cultural landscape has changed significantly. With the introduction of Self Help Groups, women are now engaged in a wide range of productive activities and are equal to men in terms of income and expenditure. Women have been given a dignified place in the family and society through the SHG movement. Their decision-making power has been greatly enhanced not only in the family but in the society as well. While the SHG movement has made progress in India, there is still a considerable amount of work to be done to empower women in all aspects of society. This is essential for the well-being of the family and the nation as a whole.

In conclusion, women empowerment is a complex and multifaceted issue. However, there are a number of factors that can contribute to it, including access to education and employment, access to credit and financial services, and participation in self-help groups. SHGs are a powerful tool for women empowerment and have been shown to have a positive impact on women's lives.

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